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Evaluation of the therapeutic and protective properties of agomelatine in an experimental rat spinal cord injury (SCI) model

Murat Kayabaş^{1*}, Güven Kılıç², Seyit Ali Bingöl³¹Sincan Education and Research Hospital, Neurosurgery Clinic, Ankara, Türkiye²Düzce University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of neurosurgery, Düzce, Türkiye³Kafkas University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Histology and Embryology, Kars Türkiye*Corresponding: muratkayabas@gmail.com

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of agomelatine treatment after spinal cord injury. A total of 24 male Sprague Dawley rats were used in the study, with 6 animals in each group. The groups consisted of 4 subgroups: control, spinal cord injury (SI), spinal cord injury-agomelatine (SI-A), and agomelatine (A). The control group underwent laminectomy only at the T7-T9 level. In the SI group, following T7-T9 laminectomy, the dura was left intact and the spinal cord was compressed with the Tator and Rivlin clip method for one minute. In the SI-A group, following T7-T9 laminectomy, the dura was left intact and the spinal cord was compressed with the Tator and Rivlin clip method for one minute, followed by seven days of 20 mg/kg oral agomelatine treatment. In the A group, laminectomy was performed at T7-T9 followed by seven days of 20 mg/kg oral agomelatine treatment. On the seventh day, the surgical wound was reopened, and the injured spinal cord was carefully removed. Histopathological examination of the spinal cord samples was performed. The control group showed a normal histological appearance. In the SI group, an increase in hemorrhage areas was observed in hematoxylin-eosin staining. In the SI-A group, a decrease in hemorrhage areas was observed compared to the SI group. No abnormal structures were found in the A group. In conclusion, agomelatine administration after spinal cord injury has shown a therapeutic effect in spinal cord injury.

Keywords: Spinal cord injury, agomelatine, laminectomy, rats

1. Introduction

Spinal cord injury (SCI) is a complex health problem affecting both physical and mental health. The etiology of SCI is often linked to traumatic events such as falls, car accidents, or sports injuries, leading to immediate physical damage and further secondary injury processes. These events disrupt brain circuits, causing varying degrees of motor, sensory, and autonomic dysfunction and significantly impacting the quality of life of those affected.^{1,2} The complex nature of spinal cord injury often leads to secondary complications, including ongoing pain, muscle wasting, and mental health issues such as depression and anxiety. The underlying biological processes of spinal cord injury involve a complex interplay of cellular and molecular responses. Following an injury, the blood-spinal barrier is disrupted, leading to increased permeability and inflammatory reactions that worsen tissue damage.^{2,3} A significant consequence of spinal cord injury is the formation of fibrotic scars, composed primarily of fibroblasts, which can hinder functional recovery by preventing axonal regeneration.⁴

Additionally, natural mechanisms that repair long nerve pathways, such as the corticospinal and rubrospinal pathways, hinder healing efforts. Given the limited chance of spontaneous healing after spinal cord injury, developing effective treatment methods is crucial. Neuropro-

TECTIVE strategies focus on preserving nerve tissue, while neuroregenerative approaches focus on assisting healing and repair processes. Agomelatine acts as an agonist for melatonin receptors MT1 and MT2 and functions as an antagonist for serotonin 5-HT_{2C} receptors. Agomelatine's dual effect its capacity to simultaneously improve sleep quality and regulate circadian rhythms is particularly important in the context of depressive disorders, as these conditions frequently lead to disruption of the circadian rhythm.^{5,6} Furthermore, agomelatine's antagonism of 5-HT_{2C} receptors has been shown to increase norepinephrine and dopamine levels in the prefrontal cortex, which are critical for mood and cognitive function.^{7,8} Beyond its effect on neurotransmitter systems, agomelatine has demonstrated the capacity to reduce oxidative stress by neutralizing reactive oxygen species (ROS) and enhancing antioxidant defenses, a feature particularly prominent in neurological conditions.^{9,10} Evidence supports that agomelatine can modulate inflammatory responses by inhibiting macrophage infiltration and protecting endothelial cells from damage in stroke models, highlighting its broad role in neuroprotection.^{11,12} Collectively, these findings position agomelatine as a promising candidate for the treatment of spinal cord injury. This study aims to investigate the therapeutic and protective effects of agomelatine in an experimental rat spinal cord injury model.

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2. MATERIALS and METHODS

Animal research was conducted at the Kafkas University Experimental Animals Application and Research Center. Twenty-four male Sprague Dawley rats, each four months old and weighing approximately 225-250 grams, were used in the study. The rats were housed in a room maintained at an appropriate temperature. The animals were fed ad libitum. The rats were divided into four groups, each containing six rats.

Group 1 (Control): Laminectomy only at the T7-T9 level.

Group 2 (Spinal Cord Injury (SI)): Following T7-T9 laminectomy, the dura was left intact, and the spinal cord was treated with the Tator and Rivlin clip compression method for one minute.¹³

Group 3 (Spinal cord injury-agomelatine (SI-A)): Following T7-T9 laminectomy, the dura was left intact and the Tator and Rivlin clip compression method was applied to the spinal cord for one minute, followed by seven days of 20 mg/kg oral agomelatine treatment.¹⁴

Group 4 (Agomelatine (A)): Laminectomy at T7-T9 followed by seven days of 20 mg/kg oral agomelatine treatment.¹⁴

Surgical Procedure

Ketamine (80 mg/kg; Ketalar, Parke-Davis-EczACIBAI, Istanbul, Turkey) and xylazine (10 mg/kg; 5 mg/kg; BioVeta, Ankara, Turkey) were administered intramuscularly to all subjects for anesthesia. Participants were placed in the prone position and kept warm with a heating lamp to maintain their body temperature at 37°C throughout the procedure. A rectal temperature probe was used to monitor body temperature. After shaving the dorsal region, a local antiseptic was applied using povidone-iodine, and a midline incision was made at the T6-11 thoracic levels. The paravertebral fascia was crossed, and the muscles were separated laterally by blunt dissection to expose the T7-10 laminae. Then, complete laminectomy was performed carefully to avoid damaging the dura mater. Hemostasis was achieved with bipolar cautery. All rats in which a dural defect was detected during the procedure were excluded from the study. The epidural space was laterally expanded according to the standard spinal trauma model (Rivlin and Tator; Spinal Cord Trauma Model).¹³ In Group 2, subjects received conventional trauma treatment with a Yaşargil aneurysm clip (Yaşargil Fe 750, Valley, Aesculap, PA, USA), applying 63 grams of pressure to encircle the dura and spinal cord for one minute. After clip removal, the

wound was anatomically closed following hemostasis. Subjects were then generally allowed to awaken, and surgery was terminated upon confirmation of normal neurological function. On the seventh day, after administration of a lethal dose of pentobarbital (200 mg/kg; Biorta, Ankara, Turkey), the surgical wound was reopened, and the injured spinal cord was carefully removed. Histopathological examination of spinal cord samples was performed.

Histological Analyses

For histopathological examination of spinal cord tissue in all groups, tissue processing and staining procedures were performed after immersion in 10% formaldehyde for 72 hours. Samples were dehydrated by washing in running water for 4 hours, followed by passing through increasing concentrations of alcohol series. Subsequently, clearing was performed by passing through xylene series, infiltration was performed by passing through paraffin series, and the tissues were embedded in paraffin blocks. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was performed.

3. RESULTS

Group-1 showed a normal histological appearance in hematoxylin-eosin staining. Group-2 showed an increase in hemorrhage areas in hematoxylin-eosin staining. Group-3 showed fewer hemorrhage areas in hematoxylin-eosin staining compared to Group-2. In Group-4, no abnormal structures were observed in hematoxylin-eosin staining.

4. DISCUSSION

Following mechanical injury, the spinal cord undergoes primary damage characterized by neuronal destruction. This damage initiates various secondary injury processes, predominantly grouped as inflammation, cell death (apoptosis), and myelin loss. The inflammatory response is one of the earliest responses to spinal cord injury (SCI). The damage activates microglia and astrocytes, the main glial cells in the central nervous system (CNS). Microglial cells, acting as immune cells, change shape and proliferate after injury. These cells then release pro-inflammatory substances such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), and interleukin-6 (IL-6), which exacerbate tissue damage. Astrocytes, the major glial cells in the CNS, also become reactive, showing an increase in size and increased glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) expression. These reacti-

Figure 1. A) Group-1, Spinal cord hematoxylin-eosin (H.E) staining, 20x magnification. B) Group-2, Spinal cord, arrow: Hemorrhage areas, 20x magnification. C) Group-3, Spinal cord, arrow: Hemorrhage areas, 20x magnification. D) Group-4, Spinal cord, 20x magnification

ve astrocytes contribute to inflammation by producing additional cytokines and chemokines, thus intensifying the inflammatory process.¹⁵ This inflammation triggers cell death, known as apoptosis, a common event after SCI. Apoptotic pathways are activated in neurons and oligodendrocytes, leading to significant cell loss. Caspases, vital enzymes in cell death, function as key mediators of apoptosis.¹⁶ Myelin loss induced by damage to oligodendrocytes prevents the maintenance of myelin sheaths around axons. The inflammatory environment exacerbates this, as pro-inflammatory cytokines can lead to oligodendrocyte death and prevent their growth from progenitor cells.¹⁷ This myelin damage reduces nerve signal transmission and contributes to functional problems in SCI patients. Along with apoptosis and demyelination, the initial inflammatory response leads to secondary damage processes that intensify neuronal damage. During the inflammatory response, excess reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced, causing oxidative stress. This, in turn, leads to cellular damage through lipid peroxidation, protein alterations, and DNA damage.¹⁸ High ROS levels result in neuronal death and sustain inflammation by activating additional pathways that further enhance inflammatory responses, creating a damaging cycle. High levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β can further stimulate microglia and astrocyte activation, increasing ROS production and inflammatory agents.¹⁹ This progression results in significant neuronal damage and functional impairment. The antioxidant properties of agomelatin have been extensively documented. Agomelatin has been shown to increase the activity of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase, while also reducing ROS production and lipid oxidation.^{9,20} Agomelatin's protective effects extend to various organ systems, including the brain, liver, and kidneys, where it has been shown to mitigate the consequences of oxidative stress.²¹ For example, agomelatin has been shown to prevent neuronal damage and improve cell survival through antioxidant mechanisms in cerebral ischemia models.²² Research indicates that agomelatin significantly alters neurotrophic factor expression, promoting neuronal survival and recovery in damaged spinal cords.²³ Furthermore, agomelatin, as a melatonergic and serotonergic agent, offers a versatile treatment option that not only alleviates depression but also provides neuroprotection by modulating inflammation.²⁴ Additional evidence shows that agomelatin treatment significantly reduces cell death markers in neural cell cultures, highlighting its protective effects.²⁵⁻²⁷ This study found that rats with spinal cord injury treated with agomelatin exhibited a marked reduction in apoptosis, consistent with existing literature. Research suggests that serotonin can exacerbate inflammation and hinder healing from injuries. For example, studies show that serotonin can disrupt axon regeneration in spinal cord injury models, suggesting that its signaling may interfere with repair mechanisms and inflammatory responses.²⁸ Agomelatin, an atypical antidepressant, is notable for its unique mechanism of action involving the 5-HT_{2C} receptor. This feature suggests potential for a multifaceted treatment strategy that can address both the psychological and physical aspects of SCI. Observed benefits of agomelatin include improved neuroprotection, enhanced mood, and a reduction in the negative effects

of serotonin on inflammation. This comprehensive therapeutic approach offers a promising avenue for addressing the complex pathophysiology of SCI. It is particularly relevant in spinal cord injury. Given the central role of neuroinflammation in various mental health disorders²⁹, the inclusion of agomelatin in treatment protocols for spinal cord injury has the potential to enhance recovery by addressing both physical and emotional aspects.

5. Conclusion

Agomelatin treatment was applied after spinal cord injury and the results were evaluated histopathologically. The findings of this study demonstrate that agomelatin, in addition to its antidepressant effects, may also contribute to recovery in spinal cord injury models. Its neuroprotective properties, its effect on neurotransmitters, and its potential to accelerate recovery through apoptosis modulation, as demonstrated in this study, position agomelatin as a promising avenue for further exploration.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, M.K. and G.K.; methodology, M.K., G.K. and S.A.B.; investigation, M.K.; analysis and interpretation, M.K., G.K. and S.A.B.; writing—original draft preparation, M.K.; writing—review and editing, M.K., G.K. and S.A.B; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Ethical approval

All experiments were performed in accordance with the guidelines for animal research from the National Institutes of Health and approved by the Kafkas University Animal Experiments Local Ethics Committee, Kars (Code No:2018/014).

Informed Consent Statement

Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement

Data is contained within the article.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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